

MOTIVATION OF ACTIVITIES IN MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: Motivation is a mental factor that gives purpose and direction to people's actions. Directing the employee is aimed at combining functions such as coordination, communication and distribution, such as the management function. The management function is the manager's mind, the more complex and differentiated the management function of his central nervous system is, the more the leadership is faced with the task of improving management both within and across functions.

Key words: motivation, employee, leadership, management.

Motivation is a mental factor that gives purpose and direction to people's actions. Directing the employee is aimed at combining functions such as coordination, communication and distribution, such as the management function. The management function is the manager's mind, the more complex and differentiated the management function of his central nervous system is, the more the leadership is faced with the task of improving management both within and across functions. As a result, a private function is gradually separated from the management function as an independent function of improving management - this function is motivation, that is, aligning people's activities with the goal by spiritual means. In this case, it is to stimulate the development of the skills of managing the employee for purposeful, effective and productive work. Mental factors occur among managers and employees.

If we talk about leaders who motivate management, they are human direct motivation to achieve organizational goals. Motivation is a dynamic process

of inciting to action.

Different theories of motivation in the psychological and organizational economic direction can be divided into two groups:

1. The meaningful theory of motivation is based on the identification of the internal motivation of a person that forces him to work in the same way and not differently (this is the term of A. Maslow and F. Hersberg and others).
2. The procedural theory of motivation is one of the most modern methods, which is based on how people know themselves and behave in the sense of education (this is Porter-Lowlam's expectancy theory, justice theory and motivation models). Although the listed theories differ from each other in some issues, they do not negate each other.

He distinguishes the five most basic of different needs: Physiological needs. The need for security and confidence in the future. Social need (support of belonging to the team in the team). The need for respect. 0 need for self-expression. According to Maslow's theory, all needs can be arranged according to a strict hierarchical structure. It requires the satisfaction of lower-level needs, which in turn affects human behavior, and higher-level needs gradually affect it.

The theory of motivation is recommended by Fredrik Harsberg, and the primary sources of dissatisfaction are: company policy, supervision, working conditions, salary, legal status, relationship with family and young workers, and secondary if there is job security. , that is, the sources of high satisfaction are: achievement, respect, job satisfaction, responsibility, promotion and growth. Harsberg concludes that a smart leader works based on both factors. This theory does not contradict Maslow's theory. A manager should not interfere in many things, but it is a mistake if he notices that he is doing something wrong and does not prevent it. A critical part of motivation is to provide positive reinforcement when things are going well. Psychologists believe that punishment should be used sparingly and balanced with incentives for good performance.

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Scanlon's plan helps to avoid such a negative situation as inappropriate incentives due to jealousy, the essence of which is that if the adoption of an idea leads to an increase in labor productivity, this idea will eliminate the problems of the idea. Rewarding prevents immediate resentment.

If the workplace is dirty, dark, and unsightly, it reduces the desire to work.

If the workplace is clean, flawless from an ergonomic point of view, clearly expressed motives for work appear. Harsberg believes that this factor is related to "hygienic" factors. Money also plays a big role. But money as a measure of human dignity is very dangerous. If the pursuit of money completely takes over a person, it creates a tendency to multiply and forces him to prove his superiority over others, as a result of which he is separated from the community and people.

Within the framework of procedural theory, how a person distributes his actions and chooses a certain type of behavior to achieve a specific goal. Procedural theory does not claim the existence of needs, but believes that human behavior is determined not only by them, but also by social needs.

There are three main procedural theories of motivation: expectancy theory, equity theory, and the Porter-Lawler model. The main meaning of the expectancy theory is the expectation of a person, because he believes that the type of behavior chosen by him will satisfy his desire. Expectation is a person's assessment of certain events. Expectancy theory suggests three interrelationships: Labor input - result; the result is a reward; reward is valence. The theory of justice answers how people distribute and direct their efforts to achieve a goal. The conclusion of the theory of justice in management practice is that if people do not have enough eyes to receive a fair reward, they will try to reduce labor activity. But the manager should not forget that the assessment of justice is not absolute, but relative.

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